

MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS IN THE NAVA DURGĀ PERFORMANCE IN BHAKTAPUR: A CASE STUDY OF NEWAR MUSIC PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

This essay examines the musical instruments played in the Nava Durgā performance, a Hindu tradition practiced by Newar people of Bhaktapur, Nepal. Due to rigorous restrictions enforced by the dancers and musicians, there is a dearth of investigation into these instruments among existing studies. While the Nava Durgā performance shares certain common traits with other Newar musical practices, several distinct aspects set it apart from other local music traditions and highlight its significance in Newar culture. Drawing from six years of fieldwork, this essay aims to bridge the gap in previous studies about the Nava Durgā performance by delving into three unexplored aspects of the musical instruments: their morphology in relation to religious symbolism; the specificity of their execution; and their function within the Nava Durgā performance and the broader social context. The analysed musical instruments and sonorous objects include the drum *dyokhin*; two pairs of brass cymbals known as *tāḥ* and *kansa*; the hourglass-shaped drum *ḍamaru*, as well as rattles *ghanḡhalā* and *chānp*. The analysis integrates detailed ethnographic descriptions with audio-visual materials collected during fieldwork. Beside the objective of complementing existing ethnographic studies on the subject, these materials aim to provide an in-depth understanding of Newar music practice through a sensorial experience and to convey oral and material knowledge in a non-written form.

Strumenti musicali nella rappresentazione della Nava Durgā a Bhaktapur: un caso di studio sulla pratica musicale Newar. Il saggio esamina gli strumenti musicali e gli oggetti sonori impiegati nella performance delle Nava Durgā, una tradizione Hindu praticata dal popolo newar di Bhaktapur, in Nepal. A causa delle rigorose restrizioni imposte dai danzatori e dai musicisti, gli studi che hanno indagato questi strumenti sono pochi. Sebbene la performance delle Nava Durgā condivide alcuni tratti comuni con altre pratiche musicali newar, presenta aspetti specifici che la distinguono dalle altre tradizioni e ne sottolineano la rilevanza all'interno della cultura newar. Basandosi su sei anni di ricerca sul campo, il saggio si propone di colmare le lacune degli studi precedenti, approfondendo tre dimensioni ancora inesplorate sugli strumenti musicali: la loro morfologia in relazione al simbolismo religioso; le tecniche esecutive; la loro funzione sia all'interno della performance delle Nava Durgā sia nel più ampio contesto sociale. Gli strumenti musicali e gli oggetti sonori analizzati comprendono il tamburo *dyokhin*, due coppie di cembali di ottone, *tāḥ* e *kansa*, il tamburo a clessidra *ḍamaru*, i sonagli *ghanḡhalā* e *chānp*. Le descrizioni etnografiche sono accompagnate da materiali audiovisivi raccolti durante il lavoro sul campo. Il saggio mira quindi ad offrire una comprensione più approfondita della pratica musicale newar anche grazie ad un approccio multimediale che consente di trasmettere le conoscenze in modalità non scritte.

1. CULTURAL CONTEXT

This essay focuses on the musical instruments and sonorous objects used in the Hindu ritual performance Nava Durgā, a representative musical tradition of the Newar people in Bhaktapur, Nepal. This city is located in the Kathmandu Valley, Nepal, approximately 15 kilometres from the capital, Kathmandu. Bhaktapur has a population around 80,000, primarily composed of Newars, an ethnic group who claim to be indigenous to the valley. The Newars distinguish themselves through their language, *Nepāl bhāṣa* or *Newari*, which belongs to the Tibeto-Burman language family, in contrast to Nepali – Nepal’s official language – which is part of the Indo-Aryan language family.¹

The earliest inscriptions in Nepal that mention Bhaktapur date back to the Licchavi period (4th-8th century), during which the city was known as *Khoprñ* or *Khvapa*, a Newar term meaning “good food”.² The current name, Bhaktapur, is a Sanskrit compound derived from *bhakta* (devotion) and *pur* (developed town). It first appears in a manuscript titled *Kiran Tantra*, dated to 924, in reference to the city (Shrestha 2016: 9). This name underscores Bhaktapur’s religious character and the growing influence of orthodox Hinduism (Slusser 1982, vol. I: 100-101),³ although Buddhism flourished alongside Hinduism and continues to be widely practiced by the Newars today.

The veneration to the Mother Goddesses in the Kathmandu Valley dates back to the Licchavi period. According to Shrestha (2003, cit. in Martin 2020: 97), their cult was established by King Amśuvarṇa around the 7th century. In the 12th century, King Ānanda Deva constructed shrines (*pīṭha*) to these deities along the perimeter of Bhaktapur. Represented by aniconic stones, the eight Mother Goddesses encircle the city in a *maṇḍala* structure, making the land a sacred space (Kölver 1976: 68-80; Slusser 1982 vol. I: 124; Lidke 2006: 43-45). Ānanda Deva also venerated Tripurasundarī – a form of Durgā – as his lineage deity and established Bhaktapur as the capital of the kingdom (Slusser 1982, vol. I: 125).⁴

Later, in 1326, the Indian ruler Harisimhadeva sought refuge in Bhaktapur following a Muslim invasion. His arrival introduced significant sociopolitical changes in the Kathmandu Valley, including promoting the process of Sanskritization and the

¹ The fieldwork on which this essay is based was carried out as part of author’s doctoral project (2019-2023) at the University of Bologna. The dissertation, *The ritual performance of the Nava Durgā: music and dance of the Banmālās in Bhaktapur, Nepal*, was supervised by Professor Domenico Staiti and Professor Silvia Bruni.

² These inscriptions (dating to 464), which represent the recorded history of Nepal, are found on a pillar of the Chāmṅunārāyaṇa temple, a Viṣṇu shrine located approximately seven kilometres north of Bhaktapur (Shrestha 2016:11).

³ Rather than designating a specific religion, the term “Hindu” is used here to refer to a set of religious traditions and beliefs from the Indian subcontinent that share certain common features. On the concept of Hinduism, see Michaels (2004: 12-30).

⁴ According to Shrestha, Tripurasundarī is considered the leading deity of the Nava Durgā (Shrestha 2016:13). However, it appears that Tripurasundarī was later incorporated into the preexisting group of eight local goddesses and is not among the deities represented in the actual Nava Durgā performance. As Gutschow (2017: 48) observes, «To the eight Mother Goddesses of the town, there is added a ninth, Tripurasundarī, who occupies the centre. But in the case of the Navadurgā, the ninth goddess is missing», or, as some dancers believe, she is symbolically embodied by the musical instruments used in the performance (cf. *infra*).

institutionalization of the cult of Taleju, the tutelary goddess of his lineage. A temple dedicated to Taleju was subsequently constructed in Bhaktapur, where it remains a spiritual focal point to this day (Wright 1877: 175–177; Gutschow 1993: 163; Sarkar 2017: 4, 234). Taleju is regarded as a form of Durgā and is closely associated with her epithet Mahiṣāsūramardīnī, the slayer of the buffalo demon (Slusser 1982 vol. I: 316; Toffin 2007: 327). During this period, the eight local Mother Goddesses were progressively assimilated into the figure of Taleju-Durgā – a process that reflected the broader trend of Sanskritization that characterised medieval Nepal (Regmi 1966, vol. 2: 601). Following the division of the Kathmandu Valley into three independent kingdoms – Kathmandu, Lalitpur, and Bhaktapur – in 1512, King Suvarṇa Malla of Bhaktapur established the Nava Durgā performance, assigned the Banmālā caste the ritual responsibility of embodying the goddesses (Gutschow 1993: 168). During this period, he also commissioned the construction of the Nava Durgā *dyochhen* or “house of the Nava Durgā” (Martin 2020: 97), a three-storey space where local devotees venerate the goddesses, and where the masks, musical instruments, costumes and ritual objects used in the performance are kept.

The Nava Durgā are nine manifestations of Durgā emanated from her body during her battle against the buffalo demon (cf. *supra* Mahiṣāsūramardīnī). In Bhaktapur they are worshipped as the following deities: Mahākālī, Bārāhī, Kumārī, Māheśvarī, Bhadrakālī, Brahmāyānī, Mahālakṣmī, Indrayānī, and Balkumārī.⁵ These figures correspond to the eight Mother Goddesses of Bhaktapur. The ninth Durgā, according to some *devagan*, is associated with the musical instruments used during the performance (Levy 1990:508). In addition to the nine female deities, there are also two male divine figures, Bhairava and Gaṇeśa. Bhairava is a furious manifestation of Śiva, one of the triple supreme divinities in Hindu traditions; while Gaṇeśa, the elephant-headed god, is Śiva’s son. Lastly, there are Bhairava’s two animal mounts (*vāhana*), Sima and Duma, a lion and a tiger. With the exception of Mahālakṣmī – who is represented by a silver bas-relief to emphasize her central role – the other divine figures are represented through clay masks. All these deities are embodied by male dancers, along with the three musicians, three assistants and several ritual functionaries, they are collectively called *devagan*, meaning “a group of deities”.⁶

The *devagan* change annually, but they are always selected from within the Banmālā sub-caste, whose traditional profession is that of specialists in flowers used in rituals.⁷ *Banmālā*, a Sanskrit term that also serves as the caste members’ surname, is paralleled

⁵ It is worth mentioning that Balkumārī is Kumārī in her childhood, so these two names represent one goddess. In the Nava Durgā performance, however, Balkumārī shares the same mask as Indrayānī.

⁶ The three assistants are called *Mema*, *Dhoma* and *Dhatima*. Each of them plays a specific ritual role in the Nava Durgā performance. For instance, *Mema* is responsible for playing the hourglass-shaped drum *ḍamaru*, although he is not considered as a musician (cf. *infra*). The ritual functionaries include several *Nāya*, whose number varies year by year and who are responsible for administrative matters, as well as a *Nakim*, the only female figure in the Nava Durgā performance, who oversees the daily veneration (*pūjā*) of the Durgā goddesses. For an in-depth study of the *Nakim* in the Nava Durgā performance, see Du (2019).

⁷ New members are indicated by an astrologer (*jośī*), who consults an ancient book guarded closely in secret by the *devagan* (Martin 2020: 98-99).

by the Newar title *Gāthā*, which refers to the same caste and its occupation. The *Banmālās* occupy a lower tier in the Newar caste hierarchy, classified among the marginally clean sub-castes (Widdess 2018 [2013]: 108). However, the role of embodying the *Durgā* goddesses temporarily reverses the *devagan*'s social status, as they are venerated by the devotees as "living goddesses" during the ritual cycle. This sacred role has also created a distinction within the caste: families with the right to embody the *Nava Durgā* tend to adopt the Sanskrit term *Banmālā*; while others continue to use the title *Gāthā*.⁸

Unlike the immortal deities of the Hindu pantheon, the *Nava Durgā* are ritually (re)born each year on the day of *Gathāmuga Caḥre* in July, begin their public activities during the *Dasāin* festival in October, and ritually depart on the day of *Bhagasti* in June of the following year. On *Gathāmuga*, the mask maker *Purna Citrakār* begins shaping the new clay masks using fresh earth offered by the new *devagan*, who simultaneously enter a three-month period of initiation and begin learning the dances and music. Later, during the pan-Indian festival of *Dasāin*, an elaborate liturgical program celebrating *Durgā*'s victory over buffalo demon, after receiving the musical instruments from the tantric priest (cf. *infra*) and their new masks, the *devagan* undertake a series of ritual activities to mark the *Nava Durgā*'s return to the urban space.⁹

From October to June, the *Nava Durgā* travel across twenty-one neighbourhoods in *Bhaktapur* and nineteen Newar villages, enacting a mobile ritual performance.¹⁰ Their repertoire includes abstract dances that highlight divine presence and territorial protection, as well as dramatic dances that convey moral teachings to the devotees. The ritual cycle concludes on the day of *Bhagasti* with the funeral of the *Nava Durgā*. On this day, after a six-hour long dance performed in the *dyochhen*, the masks are burned along with the *pātra*, a hemispherical ritual vessel made from a human cranial skull and the tuning paste (*khau*, cf. *infra*) scrapped from the drumheads.¹¹ Part of the ashes is scattered in the river near the shrine of *Brahmāyānī*, where the divine cycle had begun during *Dasāin*.¹² The remaining ashes are preserved and later mixed into the clay used for crafting the next year's masks.

⁸ In an interview with a *devagan* family, the son of the current *devagan* explicitly rejected the title *Gāthā*, stating: «We are not *Gāthā*, we are *Banmālā*». Interview with Amit *Banmālā*, 23 July 2022.

⁹ The celebration of the *Dasāin* festival in *Bhaktapur* spans sixteen days, from the new moon to the day following the full moon in the month of *Aśvina*, the sixth month of the Nepali calendar *Vikram Saṃvat*. This elaborate ritual program involves both local devotees and the *Nava Durgā devagan*. For an account of the principle ritual activities carried out by *bhaktapurians* in connection with the *Nava Durgā*, see Gutschow (2017b: 425–447). For a summary of the ritual activities performed by the *Nava Durgā devagan*, see Martin (2020: 104–106) and Du (2023: 52–53). For a detailed description of the rituals during the three-day climax of the *Dasāin* festival, see Du (2023: 138–149).

¹⁰ These nineteen villages either belonged to, or co-administered by, the Malla kings of *Bhaktapur* from the establishment of the *Nava Durgā* performance until the unification of the *Kathmandu Valley* in 1768 (Gellner 1995: 9; Du 2023).

¹¹ The specific location of the cremation remains unknown, as the *devagan* do not permit outsider to attend the ritual.

¹² According to Wegner (2023:171), following the funerals, the *Nava Durgā* are considered dead, but not entirely: «they are said to reside in the flooded paddy fields, taking a temporary appearance as tiny fish until the dry season arrives and the time for reincarnation as powerful protectors of *Bhaktapur*».

The ritual cycle of the Durgā goddesses enacts the Hindu concept of *samsāra* – the continuous cycle of death and rebirth – which constitutes a central philosophical and didactic message conveyed through the performance.

2. THE MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS, SONOROUS OBJECTS AND THEIR MYTHOLOGICAL MEANING

Among the various components of the Nava Durgā performance, the sonic dimension is considered the most sacred. It includes instrumental music that guides the procession and the dances, whispered mantras and the melodic recitations (*bhāṣā lhākegu*) dedicated to the Durgā goddesses.¹³ The sound, especially the musical repertoire, works as a tool to invoke the divinities and to establish the connection between *devagan* and the goddesses they embody. Furthermore, the sound creates a sacred space in which the ritual take place. As Zotter puts it,

The role of sound is also obvious throughout the performance. The deities are transferred by a high-caste Tantric ritual specialist from their pithas into the dancers, but they only move when they are driven by the sound of the musicians in their group. Accordingly, the musicians are considered the elders of the troupe. They control the deities. [...] Without the music, the ritual and its space would not exist (Zotter 2020: 132-133).

This central role of music is reflected in two aspects. First, the internal hierarchy of the *devagan*: regardless of the age, the three musicians occupy the highest positions, led by the drum player, and followed by the other *devagan*. This structure differs from that of other Newar musical associations (*guṭhī*), which are typically headed by the *Nāya* – the seniormost musical expert – and the gurus (Widdess 2018[2013]: 117-118).¹⁴ Second, the annual ritual *Ghanghalā la: lhāyegu* (receiving the *ghanghalā* rattles, see §3), conducted during the *Dasāin* festival, serves to reawaken the divine power of the musical instruments. Only once they have been reawakened, can the deities be invoked for the forthcoming ritual cycle.

Three instruments and three sonorous objects are played during the Nava Durgā performance: a two-headed barrel drum *dyokhin*; a pair of high-pitched cymbals *tāḥ*; a pair of low-pitched cymbals *kansa* (also known as *kya*); an hourglass-shaped rattle

¹³ *Bhāṣā lhākegu* refers to short compositions in Old Newar, whose semantic content is now only partially understood. These pieces are performed by the *kansa* cymbal player (cf. *infra*) either at the beginning or during the intervals of solo dance sequences. For an analytical study of the instrumental music performed during the procession and of *Bhāṣā lhākegu*, see Du (2024: 91–119).

¹⁴ However, the hierarchical superiority enjoyed by the Nava Durgā musicians appears to be limited to the liturgical domain. The *Nāya* – particularly the eldest among them – bear greater responsibility for organizing the performance, while the two gurus of music and dance exert authority over the other *devagan*. A similar case has been mentioned by Widdess (2018 [2013]: 118) among the Newar of Bhaktapur, albeit in a different context: in some *guṭhī* dedicated to the performance of *dāphā* ritual singing, the hierarchy is established on the basis of musical knowledge acquired, once again challenging the principle of seniority.

drum *ḍamaru*; and two types of body-attached rattles, *chānp* and *ghanghalā*.¹⁵ The three instruments are played by designated musicians, while the *ḍamaru* is played by the assistant *Mema*. The sound of the rattles is generated by the movements of the dancers during procession and dances. It is worth noting that only the drum *dyokhin*, cymbals *tāh* and *kansa* are referred with local terminology as *bājan* or musical instruments. They are known respectively as *khin bājan*, *tāḥ bājan* and *kansa bājan*, which are further associated to three demigods, respectively Nandin-Mahākāla, Chandī-Mahākāla and Bhṛṅgin-Mahākāla. These three are collectively considered as *Śivagaṇa*, a group of Śiva's attendants.¹⁶

Generally speaking, musical instruments in Newar culture are regarded as incarnations of Nāsaḥdyaḥ, a manifestation of Śiva and the god of music and dance (Ellingson 1990: 250; Widdess 2018 [2013]: 76, 79). He is considered the spiritual guru of both musicians and dancers. The apprenticeships and performances must take place under his blessing.¹⁷ Nāsaḥdyaḥ is typically represented in aniconic form – such as empty triangular or pentagonal holes (Fig. 1) – which are understood to signify a flight path of the music god (Wegner 2023: 12).

In Bhaktapur, Nāsaḥdyaḥ is uniquely accompanied by his destructive counterpart Haimādyah (also known as Mankah), who is believed to cause musicians to make mistakes if not properly honoured (Widdess 2018 [2013]: 205). The union between Nāsaḥdyaḥ and Haimādyah is expressed in various forms: the paired shrines dedicated to both deities found in each neighbourhood of Bhaktapur; their composite iconography in painting as a half-male, half-female figure (Fig. 2); and the double-headed drums, such as *dyokhin*, whose two membranes symbolizes the opposing characteristics of Nāsaḥdyaḥ and Haimādyah.

Before introducing each instrument and sonorous object, it is necessary to clarify that the names used here follow the common usage among the *devagan*. However, when compared with previous studies on the Nava Durgā performance in Bhaktapur, inconsistencies emerge regarding the *kansa* cymbals: in Gutschow's study, they are referred to as *kē* (2017a: 50), whereas in Wegner's study, they are referred to as *jhyalī* (2023: 332, fig. 379). This reflects the broader inconsistencies in the identification of Newar musical instruments noted by Ballinger and Bajracharya (1960), who compared historical accounts by Campbell (1837), Wright (1877), and their own previous research (1956-1958). Ballinger (*ibidem*: 401) hypothesized that the attribution of different names to the same instrument may be due to spelling errors. He suggests that such inconsistencies likely arose during the initial encounters with unfamiliar sounds. Newar – the primary language spoken by the musicians – belongs to the Tibeto-Burman language family, whereas most British officials who first documented Newar instruments

¹⁵ According to Wegner (2023:163), *dyokhin*, *tāḥ*, *kansa*, and *ḍamaru*, were reportedly stolen from Harisiddhi and transferred to Bhaktapur during the early 16th century.

¹⁶ Personal communication with Laxmi Prasad Banmālā, 19 February 2025. It is worth mentioning that Mahākāla is Śiva in his form as the god of Time, Nandin is Śiva's bull mount, Chandī is a form of Durgā, and Bhṛṅgin is one of Śiva's attendants, known for his skeleton form.

¹⁷ For an in-depth study of the cult of Nāsaḥdyaḥ in Bhaktapur, see Wegner (2023: 11-33).

for audiences outside Nepal were linguistically oriented toward Sanskrit or Hindi. Communication challenges and difficulty of phonetically transcribing unfamiliar sounds may therefore explain the divergent spellings of the same instrument names across the three independent reports.

FIG. 1. A shrine Nāsaḥḍyaḥ in Bhaktapur. The god of music is represented by three triangular holes. Photography taken by the author in Bhaktapur, 22 September 2022.

FIG. 2. Androgynous figure of Nāsaḥḍyaḥ, with the left half depicted as male and the right half as female. The two smaller figures at the bottom represent Nandi and Bhrṅgi, evoking the demigods associated

with the *dyokhin* drum and *kansa* cymbals in the Nava Durgā performance. Image from Wegner (2023: 67).

2.1 DYOKHIN DRUM: NĀSAḤDYAḤ'S RESIDENCE

The *dyokhin* is a double-headed barrel drum made of *peepal* wood or *figus religiosa* (Fig. 3). Its two membranes, crafted from female domestic yak (Wegner 2023: 171), are tensioned with cords of the same material, arranged in a V-shaped lacing pattern. The drum does not employ any tuning rings or wedges. At both ends of the drum are metal rings to which is fastened a shoulder strap made from the hide of a buffalo sacrificed during the *Dasāin* festival. This allows the drummer to play in procession suspending the *dyokhin* drum from his neck. The drummer performs directly with the hands, without the use of sticks or any mechanical intermediaries. The *dyokhin* drum measures approximately 75 cm in length, with slightly asymmetrical heads: the wider end has a diameter of about 30 cm, while the narrower end measures around 20 cm (Kadel 2007: 124).

According to Wegner, the *dyokhin* used in Nava Durgā performance is donated by King Jitāmitra Malla (r.1673-1696). This is confirmed by the inscription carried on the drum: «Jitāmitra Malla, the Great King has made it. The auspicious day (Nepal Samvat 805 ?) [A.D. 1685] in the solar month of Baishakh [mid April to mid May]» (Wegner 2023: 171).¹⁸ Before each ritual cycle, a drum-maker from Kulu caste repairs and retightens the *dyokhin* to ensure the drum is in optimal status for performance.¹⁹

In Newar culture, the drums are believed to be the residence of Nāsaḥdyaḥ (Wegner 2023:11). Each drumhead of the *dyokhin* is gendered and associated with a different deity: the narrower side, considered male, is called *nāsa* and is linked to Nāsaḥdyaḥ; the wider, female side is called *mankā* and is associated with Haimādyaḥ (Ellingson 1990: 267; Kadel 2007: 124).

At the centre of each drumhead, a black paste known as *khau* is applied to affect the membrane's tension and enhance the brightness of the sound. *Khau* is a small black gum-like pellet composed of rice straw ash, grass, and clay, though barley and rice flour are also used in its preparation (Kadel 2007: 119). Before each performance, the drummer removes the worn-out *khau* from the membranes and replaces it with a fresh one: the dried *khau* is first scraped off, then the player gradually applies new paste from a black pellet, adjusting the quantity based on the resulting sound quality.

¹⁸ Square bracketed information has been added by the translator. The original inscription provide by Wegner is: «*śrī śrī sumati (ja)ya jitāmitra malla devasana dayakā samvata (N.S. 805?) vaiśākha śu di śubha*». The date is tentative, as the original carving is partially damaged, and is thus reconstructed by Wegner as Nepal Sambat 805 or A.D. 1685. Wegner did not offer a translation of the inscription. I am grateful to Shamsheer Bahadur Nhuchhen Pradhan for the translation.

¹⁹ The Kulu belong to one of the lowest-ranked castes within the Newar caste system. Traditionally, their profession has been drum-making, and their use of animal skins in this craft has contributed to their low social status (Widdess 2018 [2013]: 108; Levy 1990: 84).

FIG. 3. The *dyokhin* suspended on the first floor of *dyochhen*, before the *Dasāin* festival of 2022. Photography taken by the author, 19 September 2022.

The *khau* represents the life of *dyokhin* drum, following the ritual cycle of Nava Durgā. Widdess describes it as follows:

[T]he weighting of a drum-head that transforms its sound, from a dull thud or tap to booming resonance, with a clear pitch that can be tuned. This [*khau*], said Jagannath, is the life of a drum, which gives it its distinct sound. When the masks are cremated at Bhagasti, the tuning-spot of the Navadurga's drum is scraped off the drum-head and added to the ashes of the masks to be immersed in the river, thus fertilizing the fields of newly-planted rice with the power of the goddesses - a power in which the sound of the drum is evidently a vital component. (Widdess 2018[2013]: 98)

In Bhaktapur, when the Nava Durgā cycle ends, all drums with *khau* are silenced, although their *khau* is not actually removed (*ibidem*). The reason of this silence is due to the bright timber of the drums with *khau*, which is considered unadjusted to the mourning atmosphere followed by the Nava Durgā's funerals.

Various objects with religious meaning are also placed on the *dyokhin* drum to emphasise the sanctity of this instrument. At the centre of the drum sit a pair of twisted goat horns, which represent the most iconic symbol of Nāsaḥdyaḥ in Newar culture (Ellingson 1990: 244). Between the two horns is a conical metal ornament known as *gajur* - a term that refers to the temple's spire, a distinct feature of Newar architectural style (Gmińska-Nowak 2014: 11). According to the *devagan*, the *gajur* on the *dyokhin* emphasizes the instrument's supreme ritual status among those played in

other contexts.²⁰ Furthermore, the presence of the *gajur* symbolically links the *dyokhin* to the temple, highlighting its sacred nature.

Attached to the *gajur*, the drummer ties a pouch that serves as a container for ritual offerings. Positioned in front of the horns is a small metal mask depicting Nāsaḥḍyaḥ (Fig. 4).²¹ This is consistent with the observations of Kadel (2007: 124) and Ellingson (1990: 246): in both Newar Buddhist and Hindu contexts, it is customary to decorate the *dyokhin* drum with a divine face, represented either through painting or metal relief.

Beneath the divine face is a rectangular pouch attached to the drum, containing two small tins of *mwaḥanī* and a metal applicator stick. *Mwaḥanī* – an abbreviation of *mwaḥanī sinhaḥ* – is a Newar term referring to a form of divine charm. It is a black paste composed of soot from an oil lamp, mustard, and clarified butter (Toffin 2007: 89). *Mwaḥanī* serves as another symbol of Nāsaḥḍyaḥ. Before each performance, the *devagan* apply the *mwaḥanī* to their foreheads using the metal stick, drawing a vertical mark. This act is believed to transition the *devagan* into their divine state (Wegner 2023: 163, 168).

At the lower base of the instrument, between the tensioning cords, there is a small straw cushion that allows the drum to rest on the ground during dances, enabling the drummer to perform while seated with crossed legs. On the front of the drum, also between the cords, several paper ribbons are inserted. These ribbons measure approximately five centimetres in width and forty centimetres in length, and are painted with depictions of divine figures (Fig. 5).²²

In Indian musical traditions, drum sounds are represented by syllables – an ancient practice still preserved today. These syllables, used in musical notation and oral transmission, are known as *bolī*, which indicates various qualities of the sound, such as tone, timbre and dynamics (Clayton 2000: 48). Furthermore, the syllables distinguished by opposing phonetic qualities also indicate specific playing techniques, as Rowell notes:

[T]he distinction between aspirated and unaspirated makes it possible to articulate certain significant oppositions: left and right (hand or foot), drumheads of higher and lower pitch, stress and nonstress, damped and undamped strokes, two-hand strokes as opposed to single-hand strokes. The only other prominent phonetic opposition in the traditional drum languages is that between voiced and voiceless consonants, especially d as opposed to t. (Rowell 1992: 72)

²⁰ Personal communication with Laxmi Prasad Banmālā, 29 August 2022.

²¹ The identity represented by this mask was confirmed by several *devagan* during my fieldwork. However, according to Wegner (2023: 163), the silver mask represents the goddess Mahākālī, although the author does not specify the source of this identification. If the mask does indeed depict Mahākālī, its iconography diverges significantly from the more commonly skeletal representation of this goddess.

²² In a photograph taken by Wegner in 1983 (2023: 164), the paper ribbons used at that time appear to be twice as wide and decorated with two vertical painted lines. However, the divine figures depicted remain unchanged.

FIG. 4. Details of the ritual objects affixed to the *dyokhin*: the *gajur*, positioned between a pair of twisted goat horns; the metal mask of *Nāsaḥḍyaḥ*; and the leather pouch containing two tins of *mwaḥanī* and an applicator stick. Photography taken by the author, 20 December 2019.

FIG. 5. A paper ribbon inserted between the tension cords of *dyokhin*. Photography taken by the author, 3 October 2022.

In Newar culture, *bolī* are considered vocal expressions of Nāsaḥḍyaḥ himself (Bernède 2016: 281). As such, the *bolī* used in the Nava Durgā repertoire are considered sacred and are transmitted orally only from guru to the initiated *devagan*, who strictly maintain secrecy around their musical knowledge.²³ Consequently, detailed studies on the performance technique and teaching syllables for the *dyokhin* drum are currently lacking. However, *bolī* used in other Newar drumming traditions have been discussed in previous studies (Wegner 1992; Widdess 2006; Handerson 2009; Bernède 2016). Among these, the syllables employed in *lālākhī* drumming may serve as a useful point of comparison for understanding *dyokhin* practice, as the two drums share the same morphological structure – differing primarily in the size of the *khau* paste applied to the membranes.²⁴ In the case of the *lālākhī* drum, the *khau* covers more than half the membrane’s diameter, while in the *dyokhin* drum it covers less than a quarter.

Below is a brief introduction to the *bolī* used in the learning of the *lālākhī* repertoire (Fig. 6). This knowledge was acquired during my fieldwork in 2017 through an apprenticeship with the drummer Indira Lachhimasyu. It is important to note that *bolī* may vary from neighbourhood to neighbourhood, even for the same instrument.

A total of seven syllables is used in learning: *ti, di, nan, kha, gha, dan, dha*.

Hand	Syllable (<i>bolī</i>)	Sound	Performance Technique
Right	<i>ti</i>	dampened	The hand strikes with a firm, controlled motion
	<i>di</i>	undampened	The hand strikes the centre of the membrane (near the <i>khau</i>) and immediately rebounds
	<i>nan</i>	undefined	The index finger strikes the edge of the membrane with an upward motion
Left	<i>kha</i>	dampened	The hand strikes with a firm, controlled motion
	<i>gha</i>	undampened	The hand strikes the centre of the membrane (near the <i>khau</i>) and immediately rebounds
Both hands	<i>dan</i>	undefined	The left-hand technique producing <i>gha</i> combines with the right-hand technique for <i>nan</i>
	<i>dha</i>	undefined	The left-hand technique producing <i>kha</i> combines with the right-hand technique for <i>nan</i>

FIG. 6. Performance technique of *lālākhī* drum and the corresponding syllables.

²³ The restriction surrounding musical knowledge is strictly upheld even by the scholars who maintain close relationships with the *devagan*, as noted by Wegner (2023: 163): «As a resident of Bhaktapur I was obliged to respect their rules and over the years we became friends. [...] But discretion had to be maintained. Sorry, dear reader, but the study of the music of the Navadurgā remains to be documented by a future ethnomusicologist – possibly of educated Gāthā background». It is worth noting that, although some knowledge about the musical instruments was revealed during my fieldwork, the *bolī* used in *dyokhin* drum learning, along with the entire process of repertoire transmission, remained concealed from the researcher.

²⁴ The *Lālākhī* and *dyokhin* belong to the same subclass within the Hornbostel-Sachs classification system (211.22, 81), they are unmediated percussion barrel drums, featuring membranes tensioned with laced cords without any tuning device. Moreover, as with the *dyokhin*, the *khau* paste is applied to both drumheads of the *lālākhī* to tune the timbre.

As shown in Figure 6, voiced syllables *di* and *gha* represent open, resonant strokes, while voiceless syllables *ti* and *kha* correspond to muted strokes. Non-aspirated syllables *ti* and *di* indicate right-hand techniques, while aspirated syllables *kha* and *gha* represent left-hand techniques – mirroring the phonetic oppositions traditionally used to distinguish between contrasting sounds and methods of execution.

Moreover, as Rowell (1992: 142) notes, the same drum stroke may be represented by different syllables, and conversely, a single syllable may refer to multiple strokes. In the case of *lālākhī bolī*, for instance, when the intensity of the stroke associated with the syllable *ghe* decreases, the syllable is replaced with *gao*. The use of syllables facilitates memorization of the repertoire by performers. During my apprenticeship, each new musical phrase was introduced by my teacher through a vocal phrase composed of *bolī*, accompanied by gestures marking strong and weak beats. Instruction alternated between playing the drumming and vocal recitation, with the latter forming a foundational part of the learning process.

Although the precise *bolī* used for the *dyokhin* drum remain unknown due to the *devagan*'s commitment to secrecy, it is reasonable to hypothesize a close affinity between *lālākhī* and *dyokhin* in terms of both syllabic structure and pedagogical function. Based on my field observations, at least four distinct types of sounds are produced on the *dyokhin* drum through different techniques: two muted tones created by forceful strikes to the drumheads, and two brighter, more resonant sounds created by striking the centre of drumheads near the *khau*.

2.2 TĀḤ CYMBALS

The *tāḥ* is a pair of thick-walled cymbals made from a brass alloy known as *pancha dhātu*. The name of the instrument derives from the Sanskrit term *tāla*, which denotes both musical rhythm and cymbals themselves (Widdess 2018 [2013]: 39). Each cymbal measures about 10 cm in diameter and 0.5 cm in thickness (Kadel 2007: 169).²⁵

The *tāḥ* cymbals used in the Nava Durgā performances are associated with Chandī-Mahākāla, a demigod who belongs to Śiva's retinue of assistants (*Śivagana*, cf. *supra*). They display a distinct appearance compared to those played in other musical contexts in Bhaktapur – such as *dāphā bajan*, *Bhairava pyākhan*, and *Devī pyākhan*, in which the two cymbals are typically connected by a simple leather strap. The *tāḥ* used in the Nava Durgā performance is ornamented in a distinctive way. A leather strap passes through the central hole in the dome of each cymbal, with both ends tied together on the inner side of the dome, forming a loop that serves as the base of the handle. Attached to this strap is a long-braided cord in five colours,²⁶ connecting the two cymbals (Fig. 7). Multiple layers of cloth – first white, then red – are tightly wrapped around the leather loop to create a thick, durable handle.

²⁵ The *tāḥ* cymbals are classified in the Hornbostel-Sachs system as idiophones, concussion vessel clappers with everted rims (111.142).

²⁶ The five colours are black, red, white, yellow and green. These are the same colours used in the Nava Durgā's masks and costumes.

FIG. 7. Preparation of the musical instruments on the day of Mahāṣṭamī. The *tāḥ* player attaches the long-braided strap to the leather loop that forms the cymbal handle. Photography taken by the author, 3 October 2022.

Tāḥ is the instrument that articulates the rhythmic structure of the repertoire. In the context of the Nava Durgā performances, the only technique observed involves striking the rim of the right-hand cymbal against the boss of the left-hand cymbal. This technique produces a bright, ringing sound represented by the syllable *tin*.

2.3 KANSA (OR KYEA) CYMBALS

The *kansa* is a pair of thin-walled brass cymbals, each approximately 20 cm in diameter and 0.3 cm thick. A central hole in each cymbal is threaded with a red fabric-wrapped leather handle (Fig. 8). The two cymbals are not joined together.²⁷ Similar to the *tāḥ* cymbals, the mythological significance of the *kansa* is revealed through their association with the demigod Bhr̥ṅgin-Mahākāla, who likewise belongs to Śiva's retinue of assistants (cf. *supra*).

For the *devagan* and the devotees of Bhaktapur, the *kansa* cymbals used in the Nava Durgā performance is regarded as a unique pair within Nepal, distinguished by its characteristic timbre.²⁸ Its thinner structure produces a sound that sets it apart from other cymbals of comparable size. For local devotees, it is precisely the sound of the *kansa* that signals the approach of the Nava Durgā procession.

²⁷ The *kansa* cymbals belong to the same Hornbostel–Sachs classification as the *tāḥ* cymbals: concussion vessel clappers with everted rims (111.142).

²⁸ Personal communication with Laxmi Prasad Banmālā, 11 February 2020.

FIG. 8. Preparation of the musical instruments on the day of Mahāṣṭamī. The *kansa* player wraps fresh red cloth to form the cymbal handle. Photography taken by the author, 3 October 2022.

The *kansa* cymbals is played using two techniques: brushing and striking. Brushing involves gently sliding the cymbals past one another, producing a dampened tone. Striking, by contrast, involves hitting the rim of one cymbal with the boss of the other, producing a brighter sound. The *bolī* associated with these strokes are *kal* and *ti* (Wegner 2023: 332). When not being used, the *kansa* player carries the instrument in his left hand wrapped in white cloth or placed them on the ground. It is worth mentioning that the *kansa* player is the only musician authorized to perform the melodic recitations (*bhāṣā lhākegu*) dedicated to the goddesses (Du 2024: 106-110).

2.4 RATTLE DRUM *ḌAMARU*

The *ḍamaru* is an hourglass-shaped rattle drum with two membranes laced together in an “X” pattern using leather straps. Two short leather cords, each with a bead attached to its free end, are affixed at the waist of the drum; and additional leather strap is used to constrict the lacing at the centre, regulating the tension.²⁹ According to Wegner (2023:302), the *ḍamaru* used in the Nava Durgā performance is a skull drum, which contrasts with the account provided by the *devagan*, who affirm that the instrument is made of metal alloy.³⁰

²⁹ The rattle drum *ḍamaru* is classified in the Hornbostel-Sachs system as a membranophone, specifically rattle drum with tension ligature (212.812).

³⁰ Personal communication with Laxmi Prasad Banmālā, 6 July 2025. Furthermore, based on my field observations, the *ḍamaru* used in the Nava Durgā performance exhibits a distinct metallic sheen on its surface, making it unlikely to have been made from a human skull. According to Sharma and Widdess (2024: 2), the *ḍamaru* may be made from a variety of materials, including wood, clay, coconut shell, bone, or metal

The *ḍamaru* is widely used across South Asian in both Buddhist and Hindu traditions. In the latter context, the *ḍamaru* is closely associated with the god Śiva, particularly in his form as Naṭarājā, the cosmic dancer who creates the universe through the drum's beats. It is also linked to Śiva's furious manifestations, such as Bhairava and Rudra, as well as various warlike female deities, including Durgā (Kramrisch 1981: 114; Brown 2014: 192; Sharma and Widdess 2024: 3; Widdess (2018 [2013]: 287-288).

In Nepal, the association between the *ḍamaru* and goddess Durgā – along with her alternative forms – is attested both in sculptures (Fig. 9 and Fig. 10) and in textual sources. Notably, a 17th-century hymn composed by King Jitāmitra Malla – the same monarch who donated the *dyokhin* currently used in the Nava Durgā performance (cf. *supra*) – invokes the power of the goddess during her cosmic battle against the buffalo demon. This hymn, translated by Widdess (*ibidem*: 286) is still performed during the *Dasāin* festival as a part of the ritual invocation of Durgā's victory:

Refrain: Victory to Caṇḍikā, protector of the King

1. *She plays the ḍamaru: [it goes] 'diṇḍima ḍṛma ḍṛma' The smiling one horribly gnashes her teeth: 'kaṭakaṭa' Kālikā, who protects the world, slew the buffalo [demon]: 'mama tama tama'.*
2. *Ambikā wears jingling anklets on her feet: 'caṃcaka caka caka' – and – 'jhaṃjhama jhama jhama' Dwelling in the cremation ground, Tārikā rescues us from danger: '[my heart goes] dhaṃdhaka dhaka dhaka'.*
3. *In battle she tears the demons apart: 'dhasī dhasī' Durgikā dwells in the forest. She is skilled in dance, beloved by all beings [lit. the thirteen directions], And admired by Brahmā and Viṣṇu.*
4. *Venerable King Jitāmitra beseeches the accessible Mother again and again: Folly, deceit, and false friendship are my failings – I worship at your feet.*

– commonly brass or copper. However, the specific type of material used in the making of the *ḍamaru* is not clarified by the authors.

FIG. 9. *Durga as Slayer of the Buffalo Demon Mahishasura* (14th-15th century), 21 cm, Nepal. A *damaru* is held in one of Durgā's left lower hands. The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York. Retrieved 6 July 2025, from <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/38341>.

FIG. 10. A statue of Ugra Chandī (18th century), a form of Durgā, located in Durbar Square of Bhaktapur. A *damaru* is held in one of her upper left hands. Photography taken by the author, 1 October 2022.

The *ḍamaru* is regarded by the *devagan* as a ritual object rather than a musical instrument.³¹ It is played by the assistant *Mema* on the following occasions: (1) at the beginning of the procession; (2) when the Nava Durgā troupe passes in front of a temple or shrine along the route; (3) upon arrival at the destination; and (4) during specific ritual moments.³² In addition, the *ḍamaru* is played by the *devagan* who embodies Bhairava in two dances dedicated to himself and to the goddess Mahākālī. In this context, the sound of the *ḍamaru* acoustically signals the divine presence, functioning as an «obligatory symbol of the god Śiva» (Hoerbuerger 1975:18 cit. in Sharma and Widdess 2024:22) and thereby underscoring the instrument's religious significance.³³

The enhanced ritual status of the *ḍamaru* is further affirmed by its placement during the performance. Based on my field observations, during each performance, it is positioned alongside three other ritual objects – the silver relief of goddess Mahālakṣmī, the *patrā*, and a mask of Śiva.³⁴ These four ritual objects are always positioned to the east of the performance space (Fig. 11), whereas the *dyokhin*, *tāḥ* and *kansa* are placed to the south. Additionally, during the annual ritual to renewing the life of instruments (*Ghanghalā la: lhāyegu*), the *ḍamaru* is notably excluded (cf. *infra*).

FIG. 11. Ritual objects used in Nava Durgā performance. From left to right: *patrā*, bas-relief of Mahālakṣmī, and *ḍamaru*. The face of Mahālakṣmī is deliberately removed, as local belief holds that uninitiated individuals should not look directly at her to avoid the potential danger. The mask of Śiva is absent from this photograph. Photography taken by author, 10 January 2020.

³¹ Personal communication with Laxmi Prasad Banmālā, 19 February 2025.

³² For instance, during the welcome ritual (*Lāsakūsa*), conducted by the *Nakim* both before the *devagan* depart from the *dyochhen* and upon their return, as well as during the ritual *Pāyo Nhyakegu*, the *devagan* receive their supernatural power from the goddess Taleju.

³³ Furthermore, as noted by Sharma and Widdess (2024: 22), in Hindu rituals the *ḍamaru* sometimes is played to disguise the sounds of secret mantras.

³⁴ This mask is smaller than the average size of the other masks used in the performance. It is not worn by any dancer but is instead either suspended from the metal frame supporting Mahālakṣmī's relief or carried by hand during the procession by the *devagan* who embodies Gaṇeśa. According to local interpretation, this is because «Gaṇeśa is Śiva's son, and he knows how to serve his father». Personal communication with Purna Citrakār, 9 November 2017.

The sound is produced by the impact of the beads against the drumheads, which occurs when the player shakes the drum with the right hand in a circular motion.

2.5 IDIOPHONIC RATTLES: *CHĀNP* AND *GHANGHALĀ*

Two types of rattles are used in Nava Durgā performance: *ghanghalā* and *chānp*, both of which are worn by the dancers during the performance.³⁵ The *ghanghalā* consists of a set of small bronze rattles worn around both calves. Approximately thirty individual rattles are arranged in six rows on a square piece of leather (Fig. 12), with each rattle measuring about 3 cm in diameter and contains a small internal pellet. With the exception of the three deities embodied by boys (Sima, Duma, and Balkumārī/Indrayānī), each deity is assigned a personal pair of *ghanghalā*. These rattles produce sound either by striking against one another directly or by means of an internal pellet striking the inner wall of the rattle.

FIG. 12. A dancer ties the *ghanghalā* rattles to his calf. Photography taken during the ritual *Ghanghalā la: lhāyegu*, 3 October 2022.

³⁵ Both *chānp* and *ghanghalā* are classified in the Hornbostel-Sachs system as shaken idiophones, specifically vessel rattles (112.13).

FIG. 13. A dancer checks the *chānp* rattles before the performance. Photography taken by the author, 9 October 2022.

The *chānp* consists of a row of eighteen silver rattles affixed to a red belt (Fig. 13). Each rattle measures approximately 6 cm in diameter and contains a small internal pellet, which generates sound by striking against the inner wall of the rattle during motion.

Over the course of the full performance, there are four specific moments in which the dancers intentionally sound the *ghanthalā* rattles by shaking their right leg, thereby emphasizing the manifestation of divine presence. The first occurs at the beginning of the performance, when the dancers assume their positions and receive veneration from the three musicians. The musicians begin by greeting one another – each touching the instruments of the other two before touching their own forehead – and then proceed to greet each dancer individually by touching the dancer’s mask, followed again by their own forehead. In response, each dancer shakes their right leg, producing the sound of the *ghanthalā* rattles. The second moment takes place at the end of each dance, when the dancer removes the mask – turning it to the right side of the head – and approaches the three musicians to offer a liturgical salutation. In the case of the *dyokhin* drum, the *devagan* bows, strikes both drumheads once, touches the musician’s outstretched hands, and then touches his own forehead. For the *tāḥ* and *kansa* cymbals, the dancer touches the instrument held by the musician and then his own forehead. In all cases, the dancer marks the gesture by shaking the right leg to sound the *ghanthalā* rattles. The third moment occurs during the “Dance to the Words” (*vasa phayegu pyākhan*), in which the two dancers embodying the animal deities Sima and Duma perform their dance while the *kansa* cymbal player recites a blessing and improvised text aloud. Since child *devagan* do not wear *ghanthalā* rattles, in this dance they are temporarily replaced by adult dancers embodying Kumārī and Bārāhī, who can wear and activate the *ghanthalā*. Throughout this dance, the dancers continuously shake their right leg, producing the

sound of the *ghanghalā* rattles and thereby accentuating the divine manifestation during the blessing ritual. The final moment occurs during the sacrifice of rooster. At this point, they dancers shake their right leg to sound the *ghanghalā*, expressing the deities' satisfaction with the offering.

The sound of the *ghanghalā* rattles, along with the music produced by the three instruments and *ḍamaru* constitutes the sonic identity of the Nava Durgā. According to the *devagan*, the *ghanghalā* is considered an object that houses the energy of the Durgā goddesses, and, as they explain, «since we wear *ghanghalā*, we are typically identified as a group of divinities (*devagan*)». In fact, each ritual cycle of the Nava Durgā begins with an initiation-like ritual entitled *ghanghalā la: lhāyegu*, during which the life force of the *ghanghalā* rattles and the three instruments (*dyokhin*, *tāḥ*, and *kansa*) is ritually renewed. This ritual takes place even before the *devagan* receive their new masks: the nine Durgā are first heard before they can be seen.³⁶

3. GHANGHALĀ LA: LHĀYEGU: RECEIVING THE GHANGHALĀ RATTLES

Like the masks, the musical instruments are ritually reawakened at the beginning of each ritual cycle of Nava Durgā. The ritual *ghanghalā la: lhāyegu* (receiving the *ghanghalā* rattles) takes place on the eighth day of *Dasāin* festival, known as *Mahāṣṭamī* or “the great eighth day”. On this occasion, a tantric priest (*ācāju*) consecrates the *dyokhin* drum, *tāḥ* and *kansa* cymbals, as well as *ghanghalā* rattles, which are then formally entrusted to the new *devagan* of the current ritual cycle ([video 1](#)). This day marks the conclusion of the apprenticeship period, which begins on the day of *Gathāmuga* and spans approximately three months.³⁷ What follows is a detailed account of the *ghanghalā la: lhāyegu* ritual as I observed it on 3 October 2022.

On the *Mahāṣṭamī*, four principal activities were undertaken by the *devagan*: the cleaning and preparation of instruments and ritual objects used in performance; the reception of the *ghanghalā* rattles from the tantric priest, followed by the sacrifice of a ram as offering to Nāsaḥḍyaḥ; the veneration of the two gurus; and the first public, though unmasked, dance of the new *devagan*. In the morning, all the *devagan* assembled at the *dyochhen* – the house of the Nava Durgā – to prepare the performance materials. Metal bracelets were polished, and the bronze crown was re-covered with fresh red cloth.

³⁶ See also Gutschow (2017a: 49): «The enactment of the story of creation of the Navadurgā starts, in a way, with sound». It is important to note that the sounds associated with certain manifestations of Durgā (Kumārī, Mahākālī, Bārāhī) differ from one another. These differences are evident in the rhythmic patterns performed during their solo dances, as well as in the melodies and texts of the *Bhāṣā lhākegu*, the melodic recitations dedicated to the goddesses (see footnote 13).

³⁷ However, according to Wegner (2023: 165), the new *devagan* practice individually at home until one month before Mahāṣṭamī. During the final month, all dancers rehearse together in the inner courtyard of the Navadurgā *dyochhen*. This account differs from what was reported by the *devagan* themselves, who stated that their training period concludes on the day of Mahāṣṭamī, and that prior to this date, they rehearse collectively only once in the *dyochhen* courtyard – on the occasion of *Cho:thā Pūjā* (also known as Gaṇeśa Caturthī), which takes place at the end of August. Personal communication with Amit Banmālā, 28 November 2022.

The young *devagan* were assisted by their fathers – senior members of the troupe – in completing these preparations. The two cymbal players removed the red ritual marks (*tikā*) applied to the instruments over the previous ritual cycle and replaced the worn handgrips. A new five-coloured braided strap was affixed to the *tāḥ* cymbals, which were then wrapped with layers of white and red fabric to form new grips. For the *kansa* cymbals, the outer fabric coverings of the handgrips were replaced with fresh red cloth.

In the afternoon, the *devagan* carried the instruments to the shrine of Nāsaḥdyah placed in Jhātapvaḥ square. The tantric priest prepared a ritual space in the square by drawing several diagrams with flour on the ground. On each diagram, a long leaf, referred to in Newar as *jela lapte*, was placed, serving as a base for each instrument and each pair of *ghanghalā* rattles. The *dyokhin* was positioned first, followed by two rows of other instruments and rattles: the front row included the *tāḥ* cymbals, the black paste *khau*, and the *kansa* cymbals; the back row consisted of eight pairs of *ghanghalā* rattles. The overall arrangement of the instruments and rattles formed a triangular pattern.

Before the instruments were handed over, the priest consecrated each one by touching various parts while murmuring mantras, then touched it with his forehead before passing it to his assistant. The three musicians sat in a row behind the *dyokhin* drum; before receiving their instruments, they scattered rice upon them and then lifted them, touching each to their own foreheads. The distribution of the *ghanghalā* followed a similar pattern: the priest touched different parts of each rattle reciting mantras, and the dancers scattered rice over each pair, taking it directly from priest's hands. Unlike the musicians, however, the dancers approached the priest individually, knelt with one knee on the ground and received their *ghanghalā* without mediation by the assistant. Moreover, while the musicians took the instruments with bare hands, the dancers were required to cover their hands with a piece of cloth when accepting the *ghanghalā* rattles.

Once the instruments and rattles were received, the *dyokhin* drummer applied the fresh *khau* to his drum, while the dancers tied the *ghanghalā* to their calves in preparation for the ram sacrifice and the first public dance of the ritual cycle. It is worth noting that the *chānp* was not yet worn at this stage; these would be put on only after the *devagan* receive their new masks two days later.

While the musicians and dancers were preparing, the *Nāya* affixed watercolour painting of the Nava Durgā goddesses to the frame surrounding the entrance to the shrine.³⁸ The ram sacrifice then started ([video 2](#)). In Newar culture, animal sacrifice may only be performed once the animal has given its consent, signalled by a full-body agitation.³⁹ To elicit this reaction, the *devagan* offered flowers to the ram while sprinkling

³⁸ The *devagan* refer to these painting simply as Nava Durgā. Gutschow (2017a: 51) provides more detailed information about them: «The pictures show two eight-armed Bhairavas, on a serpent (Unmatta Bhairava) and on a corpse (Bhīṣana Bhairava), as well as two snarling faces of spirits and eight pairs of so-called *jani-kani* pictures, with faces whose eyes and mouth corners are turned either to the right or the left, to ward off evil spirits. To this ensemble belong a further two images with the black, threatening and grotesque face of a Bhairava».

³⁹ For discussions on the sacrificial animal's consent, see Levy (1990: 328) and Martin (2020: 219–220). For a broader overview of animal sacrifice in Newar culture, see Pradhan (1986, 1996); Michaels (2016: 192–225); Owens (1993: 258–269); Levy (1990: 323–335); Dulal (2021).

water on its head and belly (Wegner 2023: 24). Once receiving the animal's agreement, the ram was slaughtered in front of the Nāsaḥdyaḥ shrine by the *devagan* embodying Bhairava, ensuring that the first jet of blood was directed towards the hole representing the god of music. At the same time, the other *devagan* gathered at the shrine, scattering rice in veneration of Nāsaḥdyaḥ. Immediately afterward, while the *devagan* of Bhairava held the ram, the others came forward one by one to drink the blood spurting from its throat. The *Nakim* remained beside the ram and sprinkled water over each *devagan* after they had consumed the blood. Meanwhile, two assistants held up large cloths to veil the scene as much as possible. The act of blood-drinking was accompanied by instrumental music performed by the three musicians.

Following the sacrifice, the instruments and three musicians were ritually venerated ([video 3](#)). The first *pūjā* was performed by the Banmālā women – female relatives of the *devagan*. The ritual included scattering rice over the instruments and musicians' heads, offering yogurt and flowers, and applying orange ritual mark (*tikā*) to their foreheads. Subsequently, the two gurus who had taught music and dance were honoured. Seated on a mat beside the instruments, they received homage from the musicians, the dancers and their relatives. Each *devagan* presented a long white cloth, which the gurus immediately worn around the heads as turbans. Additional offerings included alcohol, eggs, flowers, cap, and small denomination banknotes. Finally, multi-coloured ritual marks were applied to the gurus' faces. All dancers and the ritual functionaries (*Nāya*, *Nakim* and the three assistants) were then venerated by their relatives and devotees in the same manner. However, only the five novice dancers of current ritual cycle wore the white turban as a sign of their new statues.⁴⁰

Still within the square of Nāsaḥdyaḥ shrine, the first public performance of the Nava Durgā took place ([video 4](#)). The dances were performed without masks, both as solos and in groups: each *devagan*, except the three boys, performed a solo in succession. This was followed by the *Gaṇeśa dance*,⁴¹ and concluded with the *Bhairava dance*, involving all the *devagan*. During the performance, the dance guru was positioned facing the dancers, while the music guru stood beside the three musicians. This moment served as a public evaluation of their apprenticeship outcomes.

At the end of the performance, all *devagan* hurried towards the Nāsaḥdyaḥ shrine to conduct a final act of veneration for him. Nāsaḥdyaḥ is believed to incarnate within *devagan* throughout the ritual cycle of the Nava Durgā. The *devagan* touched the flame of the oil lamp (*āratī*) held by the tantric priest, then ran towards a stone pillar representing Bhairava located in front of the shrine. They touched the pillar with their foreheads and

⁴⁰ The veneration towards students and teachers at the conclusion of musical apprenticeship is a common practice in Newar culture. In other contexts, this ritual is known as *pirāne pūjā*, means “coming out”, and it is always followed by the students' first public performance. For *pirāne pūjā* of *dhimay* drum apprenticeship, see Wegner (2023: 22-33); for the same ritual associated with *dāphā* sacred singing, see Widdess (2018[2013]: 212-217), while for the same ritual associated with *devī pyākham* in Sanku village, see Shrestha (1996).

⁴¹ The *Gaṇeśa* dance, known as *ena jonegu* in Newar, is a group dance led by the elephant-headed god Gaṇeśa, followed by four goddesses: Brahmāyānī, Māheśvarī, Kumārī and Bhadrakālī.

rang the attached bell, which, according to local belief, alerts the deity of the player's presence.⁴²

The completion of the four ritual activities described above marks the conclusion of the initiation and apprenticeship period for the new *devagan*. The ritual and performative knowledge acquired over the three months of apprenticeship enables them to perform in public and confers upon them a divine identity. From this day onward, the *devagan* shed their human identity and assumed the names of the deities they embody.

Moreover, the ritual directed to the musical instruments consecrates them with supernatural power and reawakened their divine energy. Their sound marks the Nava Durgā's return and guides the performance over the following nine months, until *Bhagasti*, when the Nava Durgā withdraw from the visible world.

4. CONCLUSION

As examined in this essay, musical instruments and sonorous objects play a pivotal role in the Nava Durgā performance: their sound not only defines the ritual space but also enacts the union between the dancers and the deities they embody. This reflects the broader role of music in Newar culture, where it is considered «a powerful tool of communication and union, reaching out beyond the limited world of human affairs» (Wegner 2023: 24).

From the perspective of their mythological significance, the instruments used in the Nava Durgā performance both reflect a general connection to the god of music, Nāsaḥḍyaḥ, and acquire specific attributes – such as their association to the ninth Durgā and the *Śivagaṇa*. These deities are not seen but heard; they are the very entities that guide the movements of the nine Durgā through sound. It is therefore reasonable to compare the *bolī* and rhythmic patterns played on these instruments to mantra: codified ritual expressions that grant initiated humans access to the divine realm. The three musicians, as holders of this sacred and esoteric knowledge, occupy the highest positions within the *devagan* hierarchy.

Among the sonorous objects, the *ḍamaru* – representing Śiva or Durgā – plays a key role in setting the ritual order. This function echoes the myth of Śiva-Naṭarājā, who creates the universe through the rhythmic beats of the *ḍamaru*. Likewise, the *ghanthalā* rattles, whose sound signifies the dancers' divine identity, underscore the divine presence during key ritual moments. This explains why the annual ritual that renews the instruments' spiritual power is named after this very instrument.

Furthermore, the instruments serve as divine members of the Nava Durgā troupe. They not only follow the ritual calendar with precision but also shape the soundscape of Bhaktapur. During the *Dasāin* festival, the first sound heard on the day of Mahāṣṭamī marks the beginning of the use of all drums applied with *khau* paste. On *Bhagasti*, the conclusion of the final musical piece marks their cessation, creating a sonic atmosphere of mourning that accompanies the symbolic death of the Durgā goddesses.

⁴² For a detailed description of *ghanthalā la: lhāyegu* of 2013, see Gutschow (2017a: 49-53).

MULTIMEDIA CONTENTS

VIDEO

AVAILABLE AT: [HTTPS://WWW.SOUNDETHNOGRAPHIES.IT/IT/DU-2025-MULTIMEDIA/](https://www.soundethnographies.it/it/du-2025-multimedia/)

Video 1. *Ghanghalā la: lhāyegu* (1): preparation of the instruments and reception of the leg rattles [2:40]. Fieldwork: Bhaktapur (Nepal), 3 October 2022. Performer: the *devagan* who embody the Nava Durgā goddesses, the tantric priest (*ācāju*) and his assistant. Research and shooting: Shan Du.

Video 2. *Ghanghalā la: lhāyegu* (2): the sacrifice of a ram [3:15]. Fieldwork: Bhaktapur (Nepal), 3 October 2022. Performer: the *devagans* who embody the Nava Durgā goddesses. Research and shooting: Shan Du.

Video 3. *Ghanghalā la: lhāyegu* (3): ritual of veneration for the new *devagan* and their gurus [3:42]. Fieldwork: Bhaktapur (Nepal), 3 October 2022. Performer: the *devagan* who embody the Nava Durgā goddesses, their relatives and local devotees. Research and shooting: Shan Du.

Video 4. *Ghanghalā la: lhāyegu* (4): the first public performance of Nava Durgā ritual cycle [4:02]. Fieldwork: Bhaktapur (Nepal), 3 October 2022. Performer: the *devagan* who embody the Nava Durgā goddesses. Research and shooting: Shan Du.

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